

Effects of combination of Betaine and Kaempferol on Induced methionine overload in rats: Lipid profile and oxidative stress

Efectos de la combinación de betaína y kaempferol sobre la sobrecarga de metionina inducida en ratas: perfil lipídico y estrés oxidativo

Faisal Ali Lattef^{1,2} faissal.ali10106h@covm.uobaghdad.edu.iq <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0105-0929> and Khalisa K. Khudair¹ khalisakhadim00@gmail.com <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3953-7975> *Corresponding author:

¹Department of Physiology, Biochemistry and Pharmacology, College of Veterinary Medicine, University of Baghdad.

²Al- Bayan University College of Health and Medical Techniques Department of Medical Laboratory Techniques

Received: 01/20/2022 Accepted: 04/19/2023 Published: 05/12/2024 DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11261767>

Abstract

This experiment was designed to find the role of Kaempferol (KPF) and Betaine (BET) on Metabolic disturbance induced by methionine overload (lipid dysfunction and oxidative stress) in male rats. Thirty (30) adult rats were randomly selected and divided equally into five experimental groups and treated for 45 days as the follows: group G1:Rats in this group served as control, Rats in other groups (G2,G3,G4 and G5 were received 100mg/kg B.W of D-L methionine in tap water, and received orally as follows: Rats in group G3 were given 150 mg/kg b.w. of KPF, rats in group G4 were given 250 mg/kg b.w. BET, rats in group G5 were given 150 mg/kg b.w. of KPF, 250 mg/kg b.w. BET Fasting blood sample were collected by cardiac puncture technique at the end of the experiments and serum were collected for estimation serum lipid profile and Malondialdehyde(MDA). The results of the experiment showed that oral intubation of D-L methionine for 45 days(G2 group) caused dyslipidemia manifested by significant elevation in serum concentration of total cholesterol (TC), Triacylglycerol (TAG), low density lipoprotein-cholesterol(LDL-C) and very low density lipoprotein-cholesterol (VLDL-C), and significant decrease in high density lipoprotein-cholesterol (HDL-C),also caused oxidative stress manifested by increase in Malondialdehyde (MDA) concentration. while oral intubation of KPF, BET or their combination ameliorate the dyslipidemia and oxidative stress induced by methionine overload.

Key words: kaempferol, betaine, lipid profile, MDA, DI-Methionine

Resumen

Este experimento fue diseñado para encontrar el papel del Kaempferol (KPF) y la Betaína (BET) en la alteración metabólica inducida por la sobrecarga de metionina (disfunción lipídica y estrés oxidativo) en ratas macho. Se seleccionaron al azar treinta (30) ratas adultas y se dividieron en partes iguales en cinco grupos experimentales y se trataron durante 45 días de la siguiente manera: grupo G1: las ratas de este grupo sirvieron como control, las ratas de otros grupos (G2, G3, G4 y G5 recibieron 100 mg/kg p.c. de metionina D-L en agua del grifo, y se recibieron por vía oral de la siguiente manera: las ratas del grupo G3 recibieron 150 mg/kg p.c. de KPF, las ratas del grupo G4 recibieron 250 mg/kg p.c. de BET, las ratas del grupo G5 recibieron 100 mg/kg p.c. Se recogieron 150 mg/kg de peso corporal de KPF, 250 mg/kg de peso corporal de BET mediante la técnica de punción cardíaca al final de los experimentos y se recogió suero para estimar el perfil de lípidos séricos y malondialdehído (MDA). que la intubación oral de metionina D-L durante 45 días (grupo G2) causó dislipidemia manifestada por una elevación significativa en la concentración sérica de colesterol total (CT), triacilglicerol (TAG), lipoproteínas de baja densidad (LDL-C) y lipoproteínas de muy baja densidad. El colesterol (VLDL-C) y la disminución significativa del colesterol de lipoproteínas de alta densidad (HDL-C) también causaron estrés oxidativo manifestado por un aumento en la concentración de malondialdehído (MDA). mientras que la intubación oral de KPF, BET o su combinación mejora la dislipidemia y el estrés oxidativo inducido por la sobrecarga de metionina.

Palabras clave: kaempferol, betaína, perfil lipídico, MDA, DI-Metionina

Induced Methionine overload is likely to be involved in dysfunction of several organs such as kidney, heart and reproductive, which may be interrupted to HHcy¹⁻³. Homocysteine (Hcy) is a non-protein sulfhydryl-containing amino acid, and intermediate metabolite formed in metabolism of methionine⁴. Elevated level of Hcy, is an important risk factor for arteriosclerosis, Alzheimer's disease, cardiovascular disease, ischemic heart disease, stroke, liver cirrhosis, diabetic retinopathy, and diseases of the central nervous system⁵⁻⁹. (HHcy) is a methionine metabolism problem that causes a variety of inflammatory illnesses¹⁰. Oxidative stress is among the processes thought to be involved in the pathophysiology of the damage produced by HHcy, medicinal herbs and many food ingredients possess favorable biological properties that contribute to their therapeutic activities. One such natural product is BET, a stable, nontoxic natural substance that is present in animals and plants beets (*Beta vulgaris*) is a major source of betaine, it is also found at high concentrations in other food sources including wheat bran, wheat germ, and spinach¹¹, or exogenously consumed through dietary intake¹². Dietary betaine (trimethylglycine), crucial methyl donor, that restores methionine homeostasis in cells¹³. BET supplementation to broiler chicken's diet improved their productive performance¹⁴. BET plays a role in preventing/attenuating both alcohol-induced and metabolic-associated liver diseases^{13,15}. They also reported that BET has an anti-nociceptive and a sedative role through interactions with opioidergic and -aminobutyric acid (GABA) receptors¹⁶. KPF is an antioxidant flavonol found in fruits and vegetables including apples, gooseberry, carrot, honey and spinach¹⁷⁻¹⁹. KPF were recorded to be dominant compound with high concentration in some plants in the north of Iraq such as *Adiantum capillus-veneris*²⁰ and *Asplenium* species^{21,22}. KPF and its glycosylated derivatives are found to possess cardio protective²³, neuroprotective²⁴, anti-inflammatory²⁵, antidiabetic²⁶ and antimicrobial activity²⁷, in addition to its antioxidant effect²⁸. KPF, being a polyphenolic nutraceutical compound, exhibits high cytotoxicity, and thus has a promising role in cancer therapy²⁹. Researchers have indicated the antioxidant potential of KPF in both in vitro and in vivo models³⁰. It causes the scavenging of the free radicals and other ROS molecules, as their generation transforms the normal cells into malignant ones³¹. KPF reduces liver damage in acetaminophen-treated rats through its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anti-apoptotic effects³². According to available literature, several studies concerning beneficial effect of the KPF and BET and the damaging effect of the HHcy, However, there are few studies on the beneficial effect of combination of KPF and BET on the harmful effect of hyperhomocysteinemia (HHcy) (overload of Methionine).

Thirty (30) adult male rats were randomly selected and divided equally into five experimental groups and treated for 45 days as the follows: **Group G1:** Control group were received tap water.; **Group G2:** Rats in this group were given 100mg/kg B.W of D-L methionine in tap water.; **Group G3:** Rats in this group were given 150 mg/kg b.w. of KPF and 100 mg/kg B.W of D-L methionine in tap water; **Group G4:** Rats in this group were given 250 mg/kg b.w. BET and 100mg/kg B.W of D-L methionine in tap water; **Group G5:** Rats in this group were given 150 mg/kg b.w. of KPF, 250 mg/kg B.W. BET and 100mg/kg B.W of D-L methionine in tap water KPF and BET were given orally. Fasting blood (for 8-12 hrs) samples were collected at the end of the experiment (45day). Blood was drawn by cardiac puncture technique from anesthetized rats' intramuscular injection of Ketamine (90 mg/Kg B.W.) and xylazine (40 mg/kg B.W.) using the disposable syringe. Then blood samples were kept in nonheparinized tubes and let for 10 minutes for standing, Serum were obtained by centrifugation for 15 minutes at 3000 rpm and kept tightly stopper tubes frozen at - 20°C for mastering the following concentrations: total cholesterol (TC), high density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-c) and Triacylglycerol (TAG) using enzymatic kits (**Bio system, Spain**). While low density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-c) and very low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (VLDL-C) were calculated according to Friedwald formula and Malondialdehyde (MDA) concentrations using enzymatic kits (**Bio system, Spain**).

Results

Serum TC, TAG, LDL-c, VLDL-c, and HDL-c concentrations of different treated groups were summarized in Figure 1 (A,B,C,D,E) respectively. The result showed that rats given methionine overload (G2) caused significant ($p < 0.05$) increase in serum TC, TAG, VLDL-c and LDL-c with significant ($p < 0.05$) decrease in serum HDL-c concentration comparing to other treated group. While KPF, BET intubation alone or in combination (G3 to G5) showed significant decrease in lipid profile parameters except HDL-C which showed significant elevation ($p < 0.05$) comparing to other treated groups except control.

Figure 1: Effect of oral intubation of Kaempferol, Betaine/ or their combination on serum lipid profile concentrations in methionine overload rats. (A) TC, (B) TAG, (C) HDL-c, (D) LDL-c and (E) VLDL-c.

G1: Rats in this group served as control, The other experimental groups from G2 to G5 were given 100mg/kg B.W. of DL-methionine in tap water, in addition Rats in G3 group were given 150mg/kg B.W. of KPF, Rats in G4 were given 250 mg/kg B.W. of BET, Rats in G5 were given combination of 150mg/kg B.W. of KPF and 250 mg/kg B.W. of BET The mean values are presented \pm SE, n=6. Significant differences among groups are shown by different small letters ($p < 0.05$). Methionine was given in drinking water. experiment was lasted for 45 days KPF and BET were given orally.

At the end of the experiment, the result showed significant elevation ($p < 0.05$) in serum Malondialdehyde (MDA) concentrations in (G2) treated group compared with other experimental groups, which showed significant decrease in this parameter (G3 to G5).

Figure 2: Effect of oral intubation of Kaempferol, Betaine/ or their combination on serum malondialdehyde concentration (nmol/ml) in methionine overload adult male rats.

G1: Rats in this group served as control, The other experimental groups from G2 to G5 were given 100mg/kg B.W. of DL-methionine in tap water, in addition Rats in G3 group were given 150mg/kg B.W. of KPF, Rats in G4 were given 250 mg/kg B.W. of BET, Rats in G5 were given combination of 150mg/kg B.W. of KPF and 250 mg/kg B.W. of BET The mean values are presented \pm SE, n=6. Significant differences among groups are shown by different small letters ($p < 0.05$). Methionine was given in drinking water. experiment was lasted for 45 days KPF and BET were given orally.

Discussion

This study showed that DL-methionine given to male rats for forty-five (45) days lead to significant changes in lipid profile system. These changes were manifested by increase in TC, TAG, LDL-C, VLDL-C and decrease in serum HDL-C concentrations. These results are in agreement with other studies^{33,34}. The mechanism could be duo to D-L methionine overload - induced HHcy. Induction of HHcy after methionine overload in diet or water were agreed with³⁵⁻³⁹. One of the primary biological responses to HHcy includes effects on lipid metabolism such as increased expression of genes involved in de novo lipogenesis, lipolysis and fatty acid oxidation in liver and white adipose tissue⁴⁰. HHcy plays an important role in cholesterol biosynthesis by inducing transcription as well as translation of 3 hydroxy-3- methylglutaryl coenzyme A reductase (Limiting enzyme in the cholesterol biosynthesis). It also increased cholesterol synthesis and intestinal absorption and suppressed excretion of cholesterol⁴¹. Furthermore,

Hypercholesterolemia under effect of methionine overload may cause mutation of LDL receptors adaptor protein, leading to defective LDL receptors and consequent reduction in plasma LDL clearance resulting in its accumulation⁴². The increase in TAG levels in animals receiving methionine in the present study may be due to increment in plasma VLDL levels (which act as a carrier for the TAG in the plasma), partial deficiency of lipoprotein lipase, associated with increased put out of lipoproteins from the liver⁴³.

Current result showed that oral intubation of (KPF), BET or their combination caused correction of dyslipidemia induced by methionine overload indicated their hypolipidemic effect. It has been recently showed that KPF intubation ameliorates glucose and lipid metabolism disorders by enhancing lipid metabolism via Adenosine monophosphate-activated protein kinase (AMPK) activation. KPF down regulates SREBPs and up regulates liver peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor α (PPAR α), promoting the expression of propyl CoA oxidase, reducing the accumulation of visceral fat, and improving hyperlipidemia in high-fat diet-fed obese rats⁴⁴. A decrease in TAG could be duo to upregulation the expression of adipose triglyceride (TAG) lipase⁴⁵. Besides, it up regulates liver X receptor (LXR), which regulates lipid transport⁴⁶. KPF attenuates the activity and expression of CYP2E1⁴⁷, the resulting falling status of the energy supply, demonstrated by the increased ratio of adenosine monophosphate (AMP) /adenosine triphosphate (ATP), was sensed by AMPK. The activation of AMPK by KPF in turn enhanced lipolysis and inhibited fatty acid synthesis both in vivo and in vitro⁴⁸, and caused decrease in level of ALT, LDL, triglycerides, total cholesterol, lipid droplets in liver⁴⁹. Recent studies have shown that AMPK exerted its ability to regulate lipid metabolism by enhancing fatty acid oxidation, while inhibiting the production of cholesterol and fatty acids⁵⁰⁻⁵². Betaine intubation in herein has been found to be inversely correlated to a case of dyslipidemia and positively correlated to HDL cholesterol concentration indicating its hypolipidemic effect^{53,54}. BET increased plasma HDL which may reflect the favorable effects of BET on liver function-related metabolism⁵⁵. The positive effects of BET on lipid metabolism have been attributed to the fact that it is an important methyl donor, resulting in a considerable increase in hepatic SAM concentrations⁵⁶⁻⁵⁹. The increased SAM availability is thought to regulate phosphatidylcholine (PC) synthesis by PEMT and this normalizes VLDL production rates⁶⁰. BET has been used for more than 30 years in pyridoxine non-responsive cystathionine beta-synthase (pnrCBS) and cobalamin C (cblC) deficiencies to lower the HHcy⁶¹. BET may also reduce uptake of triglycerides from circulating lipoproteins by decreasing the mRNA expression of lipoprotein lipase⁶²⁻⁶⁴. BET administration could activates AMPK, which enhances genes encoding proteins involved in fatty acid transport and fatty acid oxidation, while decreasing fatty acid synthesis⁶⁵, thereby preventing triglyceride and cholesterol accumulation in the liver⁶⁶.

In the current study an elevation in Malondialdehyde (MDA) concentration was observed in G2 group indicating a case of oxidative stress. Such changes may be attributed to HHcy induced after methionine overload⁷. It has been demonstrated that mild hHCY is much more common and is associated with post methionine loading in water^{68,69} or in diet⁷⁰. Formation of ROS such as hydrogen peroxide, superoxide anions, and hydroxyl radicals and oxidative stress are among the process that involved in damage produced by HHcy^{39,71,72}. The result of the present work was correlated with⁷² and⁷⁴ who demonstrated significant increase in plasma markers of LPO in rats with HHcy resulting by induced methionine overloading. It has been reported that homocystein (hcy) reduces the antioxidant capacity of the body by inhibiting glutathione production and suppressing the expression of Glutathione peroxidase (GSH-Px) and SOD⁷⁵⁻⁷⁸. The mechanism could be strong production of ROSs has been detected at the onset of HHcys when the sulfhydryl HCys group is easily oxidized, producing superoxide anion (O⁻²) species as a result of both the activation of nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate oxidase and the inhibition of the expression and function of important antioxidant enzymes, such as superoxide dismutase and glutathione peroxidase⁷⁹. Significant decrease in serum MDA concentration was observed in BET treated group, indicating the antioxidant activity of betaine which was been documented by^{12,80,81}. One of the biological and beneficial effects of dietary BET on methyl donor, that restores methionine homeostasis in cells and reduce HHcy that affect oxidative stress. BET can enhance non enzymatic antioxidant defences, attenuate oxidative stress, endoplasmic reticulum stress by regulation of methionine metabolism via removing Hcy and maintaining cellular SAM:SAH ratios^{82,13}.

BET is a precursor of S-adenosylmethionine (SAM), which contributes to an increase in the supply of substrate needed for the synthesis of GSH⁸³. Besides, Experimental evidence suggests that SAM has direct antioxidant activity via ROS scavenging and chelation of iron ions used to inhibit hydroxyl radical generation⁵⁸. BET exerts its antioxidant properties through its ability to scavenge free radicals, or by increasing the activity of antioxidants mainly SOD^{84,85}. Additionally, the three methyl groups of BET were found to play a key role in its antioxidant activity. The possible reason was that because of the hydrophobicity of the three methyl groups and hydrophilicity of the carboxyl of BET, a tight protective membrane was formed around cells to prevent oxidative stress inducer from inducing ROS generation and cell damage⁸².

Significant decrease in serum MDA level was observed after KPF intubation in the current study. Remarkable antioxidant effects of KPF, namely acting directly in antioxidant enzymes, capable of efficiently inhibit ROS generation and lipid peroxidation, and, finally, preventing the occurrence of cell damages, in a broad-spectrum

activity, KPF is a potent scavenger of superoxide anion, hydroxyl radical, by chelating cuprous or ferrous⁸⁷, and peroxynitrite⁸⁶, it also inhibits pro-oxidant enzymes, such as xanthine oxidase⁸⁸, and activates antioxidant enzymes such as superoxide dismutase, catalase, and heme oxygenase-1⁸⁹. It is important to highlight, is that KPF contains hydroxyl groups at C3, C5, and C4, an oxo group at C4, and a double bond at C2-C3 that might explain its antioxidant activity^{86,90}. Additionally, some researchers have revealed the antioxidant ability of KPF in vivo by promoting the expression of Nrf2 and its target genes (SOD1 and GPX3), reducing ER stress and inhibiting apoptosis⁹¹. stimulation of Nrf2 and decreased ROS levels by KPF and H₂O₂ through the activation of heme oxygenase-1 (HO-1) which prevented oxidative damage in vitro⁹².

The effect of the BET and KPF combination was obviously more potent than that of KPF alone, suggesting the synergistic effect of these compounds. Combination therapy has been demonstrated to be superior to monotherapy in metabolic abnormalities such as T2DM^{93,94}. It can be hypothesized that this synergistic effect might be due to their different mechanisms of action on energy supply pathways. While both KPF and the combination of BET and KPF significantly induced the phosphorylation of AMPK, indicating the upregulation of AMPK activity that effect antioxidant activity, lipid⁹⁵ and glucose metabolism⁹⁶. Moreover, the enhancement of catabolic lipid metabolism was due to the activation of AMPK, the sensor of energy status. Hence, BET and KPF combination could regulate lipid metabolism through activation of AMPK as was recorded after combination of Cinnamaldehyde (CA) and KPF⁴⁸.

References

1. Salman, A. D. (2014). The Protective role of Pomegranate seed oil (Pometon) on kidney (functional and structural) damage induced by Methionine overload in adult female Rabbits. *The Iraqi Journal of Veterinary Medicine*, 38(2), 66-73.
2. Al-Okaily, B. N. (2014). The Role of Pometone (Pomegranate seed oil) in Ameliorating the Deleterious Effect of Methionine Overload on Some Histological Aspects of heart and aorta in Female Rabbits (Part-II): Baraa Najim Al-Okaily@ and Lekaa Najim Abdulla. *The Iraqi Journal of Veterinary Medicine*, 38(1), 62-70.
3. Al-Okaily, B. N. (2012). Protective Effect of Alcoholic extract of Black Current in Male Reproductive System of Methionine Overload Rats. *The Iraqi Journal of Veterinary Medicine*, 36(2), 187-194.
4. Demerchi, S. A., King, N., McFarlane, J. R., & Moens, P. D. (2021). Effect of methionine feeding on oxidative stress, intracellular calcium and contractility in cardiomyocytes isolated from male and female rats. *Molecular and Cellular Biochemistry*, 476, 2039-2045.
5. Rehman, T., Shabbir, M. A., Inam-Ur-Raheem, M., Manzoor, M. F., Ahmad, N., Liu, Z. W., ... & Aadil, R. M. (2020). Cysteine and

- homocysteine as biomarker of various diseases. *Food science & nutrition*, 8(9), 4696-4707.
6. Azzini, E., Ruggeri, S. and Polito, A. (2020). Homocysteine: it's possible emerging role in at-risk population groups. *International journal of molecular sciences*, 21(4):1421.
 7. Smith, A. D. and Refsum, H. (2021). Homocysteine—from disease biomarker to disease prevention. *Journal of internal medicine*, 290(4), 826-854.
 8. Cordaro, M., Siracusa, R., Fusco, R., Cuzzocrea, S., Di Paola, R., & Impellizzeri, D. (2021). Involvements of hyperhomocysteinemia in neurological disorders. *Metabolites*, 11(1), 37.
 9. Tchanchou, F., Goodfellow, M., Li, F., Ramsue, L., Miller, C., Puche, A. and Fiskum, G. (2021). Hyperhomocysteinemia-induced oxidative stress exacerbates cortical traumatic brain injury outcomes in rats. *Cellular and molecular neurobiology*, 41, 487-503.
 10. Elsherbiny, N. M., Sharma, I., Kira, D., Alhusban, S., Samra, Y. A., Jadeja, R., ... & Tawfik, A. (2020). Homocysteine induces inflammation in retina and brain. *Biomolecules*, 10(3), 393.
 11. Zhao, G., He, F., Wu, C., Li, P., Li, N., Deng, J., ... & Peng, Y. (2018). Betaine in inflammation: mechanistic aspects and applications. *Frontiers in immunology*, 9, 1070.
 12. Willingham, B. D., Ragland, T. J., & Ormsbee, M. J. (2020). Betaine supplementation may improve heat tolerance: Potential mechanisms in humans. *Nutrients*, 12(10), 2939.
 13. Arumugam, M. K., Paal, M. C., Donohue Jr, T. M., Ganesan, M., Osna, N. A. and Kharbanda, K. K. (2021). Beneficial effects of betaine: A comprehensive review. *Biology*, 10(6), 456.
 14. AL-Hameed, S. A., AL-Machi, A., & Al-Gharawi, J. K. (2020). Effect of Supplementing Betaine on Productive Performance of Broiler Chickens Fed Diets Containing Different Levels of Choline. *Systematic Reviews in Pharmacy*, 11(11).
 15. Jaffer Ramadhan, S. (2019). Effect of Betaine on Hepatic and Renal Functions in Acrylamide Treated Rats.* Ramadhan, Sadiq jaffer and khudair, khalisa khadim. *The Iraqi Journal of Veterinary Medicine*, 43(1), 138-147.
 16. Hassanpour, S., Rezaei, H., & Razavi, S. M. (2020). Anti-nociceptive and antioxidant activity of betaine on formalin-and writhing tests induced pain in mice. *Behavioural brain research*, 390, 112699.
 17. Moratalla-López, N., Lorenzo, C., Alonso, G. L., & Sánchez, A. M. (2016). Kaempferol glycosides in *Crocus*: Sources, biosynthesis, and uses. *Kaempferol: Biosynthesis, Food Sources and Therapeutic Uses*; Garde-Cerdán, T., Gonzalo-Diago, A., Eds, 151-195.
 18. Afrin, S., Haneefa, S. M., Fernandez-Cabezudo, M. J., Giampieri, F., Al-Ramadi, B. K., & Battino, M. (2020). Therapeutic and preventive properties of honey and its bioactive compounds in cancer: An evidence-based review. *Nutrition research reviews*, 33(1), 50-76.
 19. Silva dos Santos, J., Goncalves Cirino, J. P., de Oliveira Carvalho, P., & Ortega, M. M. (2021). The pharmacological action of kaempferol in central nervous system diseases: A review. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, 11, 565700.
 20. Al-Khesraji, T. O., Ismail, A. M., & Maulood, B. K. (2017). Flavonoid Contents of *Adiantum capillus-veneris* L. Growing in Two Different Districts from Iraqi Kurdistan Northern Iraq. *Egyptian Academic Journal of Biological Sciences*, H. Botany, 8(1).
 21. Ismail, A. M., AL-Amery, M. M., Abdulqader, R. S. (2022). Ecological variations affecting the chemical content in methanolic extract of three *Asplenium* species from north of Iraq. *Indian Fern J.* 39(2) : 27-33.
 22. Ismail, A. M., Hamdi, B. A., Maulood, B. K., & AL-Khasreji, T. O. (2021). An ecological study of the fern *Asplenium Trichomanes* L. in Iraq with a reference to its phytochemical and antioxidant activity. In *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* (Vol. 779, No. 1, p. 012117). IOP Publishing.
 23. Zhou, M., Ren, H., Han, J., Wang, W., Zheng, Q., and Wang, D. (2015). Protective effects of kaempferol against myocardial ischemia/reperfusion injury in isolated rat heart via antioxidant activity and inhibition of glycogen synthase kinase-3. *Oxidative medicine and cellular longevity*, 2015.
 24. Ma, Y., Liu, Y., Sun, A., Du, Y., Ye, M., Pu, X., & Qi, X. (2017). Intestinal absorption and neuroprotective effects of kaempferol-3-O-rutinoside. *RSC advances*, 7(50), 31408-31416.
 25. Alam, W., Khan, H., Shah, M. A., Cauli, O., & Saso, L. (2020). Kaempferol as a dietary anti-inflammatory agent: current therapeutic standing. *Molecules*, 25(18), 4073.
 26. Chandramohan, G., Al-Numair, K. S., Alsaif, M. A., & Veeramani, C. (2015). Antidiabetic effect of kaempferol a flavonoid compound, on streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats with special reference to glycoprotein components. *Progress in Nutrition*, 17(1), 50-57.
 27. Tatsimo, S. J. N., Tamokou, J. D. D., Havyarimana, L., Csupor, D., Forgo, P., Hohmann, J., ... & Tane, P. (2012). Antimicrobial and antioxidant activity of kaempferol rhamnoside derivatives from *Bryophyllum pinnatum*. *BMC Research notes*, 5(1), 1-6.
 28. Zeng, Z. C., Jiang, J., Wang, X. J., Wei, K. N., Liang, H. S., Zeng, L. X., ... & Wang, H. L. (2022). Kaempferol ameliorates in-vitro and in-vivo postovulatory oocyte ageing in mice. *Reproductive BioMedicine Online*, 45(6), 1065-1083.
 29. Sharma, G. S., Bhattacharya, R., & Singh, L. R. (2021). Functional inhibition of redox regulated heme proteins: A novel mechanism towards oxidative stress induced by homocysteine. *Redox Biology*, 46, 102080.
 30. Kashyap, D., Sharma, A., Tuli, H. S., Sak, K., Punia, S., & Mukherjee, T. K. (2017). Kaempferol—A dietary anticancer molecule with multiple mechanisms of action: Recent trends and advancements. *Journal of functional foods*, 30, 203-219.
 31. Wang, L., Niu, H., & Zhang, J. (2020). Homocysteine induces mitochondrial dysfunction and oxidative stress in myocardial ischemia/reperfusion injury through stimulating ROS production and the ERK1/2 signaling pathway. *Experimental and therapeutic medicine*, 20(2), 938-944.
 32. BinMowyna, M. N. and AlFaris, N. A. (2021). Kaempferol suppresses acetaminophen-induced liver damage by upregulation/activation of SIRT1. *Pharmaceutical Biology*, 59(1), 144-154.
 33. Norri, M.; Jacopues, P. and Rosenberg, H. (2001). Hyperhomocysteinemia associated with poor recall in the third national health and nutrition examination. *Survey. Am. J. Clin. Nut.* ,73:927-933.
 34. Feng, Y., Chen, Y., Yang, B., Lan, Q., Wang, T., Cui, G., ... & Lee, S. M. Y. (2019). Hepatoprotective effect of jianpi huoxue formula on nonalcoholic fatty liver disease induced by methionine-choline-deficient diet in rat. *BioMed research international*.
 35. AL-Gaborry, W. B. (2010). Protective And Therapeutic Role Of Olive Oil And Folic Acid In Some Biochemical Parameters And Histological Changes In Male Rabbits Exposed To Methionine Over Load (Doctoral dissertation, MSC., thesis, collage of veterinary medicine/University of Baghdad).

36. Luo, X., Xiao, L., Yang, H., Zhang, R., Jiang, M., Ni, J., ... & Wang, N. (2014). Homocysteine downregulates gene expression of heme oxygenase-1 in hepatocytes. *Nutrition & metabolism*, 11(1), 1-10.
37. Hrnčić, D., Mikić, J., Rasic-Markovic, A., Velimirović, M., Stojković, T., Obrenović, R., Stanojlović, O. (2016). Anxiety-related behavior in hyperhomocysteinemia induced by methionine nutritional overload in rats: role of the brain oxidative stress. *Canadian journal of physiology and pharmacology*, 94(10), 1074-1082.
38. Kumar, A., Palfrey, H. A., Pathak, R., Kadowitz, P. J., Gettys, T. W., & Murthy, S. N. (2017). The metabolism and significance of homocysteine in nutrition and health. *Nutrition & metabolism*, 14(1), 1-12.
39. D'Amico, R., Cordaro, M., Fusco, R., Peritore, A. F., Genovese, T., Gugliandolo, E., and Impellizzeri, D. (2022). Consumption of Cashew (*Anacardium occidentale* L.) Nuts Counteracts Oxidative Stress and Tissue Inflammation in Mild Hyperhomocysteinemia in Rats. *Nutrients*, 14(7), 1474.
40. Perrone, C. E., Mattocks, D. A., Jarvis-Morar, M., Plummer, J. D., & Orentreich, N. (2010). Methionine restriction effects on mitochondrial biogenesis and aerobic capacity in white adipose tissue, liver, and skeletal muscle of F344 rats. *Metabolism*, 59(7), 1000-1011.
41. Glueck, C.J.; Shaw, P.E.; Tracy, T.; Sieve-Smith, L. and Wang, Y. (1995). Evidence that Homocysteine an independent risk factor for atherosclerosis in hypolipidemic patient's. *Am J Card.*, 75:132-136.
42. Neil, J and Stone, M. (2006). *Management of Lipid in Clinical Practice*. 6 Ed., University School Chicago.
43. Hamelet, J.; Demuth, K.; Paul J.; Delabar, J. and Janel, N. (2007). Hyperhomocysteinemia due to cystathionine beta synthase deficiency induces dysregulation of genes involved in hepatic lipid homeostasis in mice. *J Hepatol.*, 46:151-159.
44. Chang, C. J., Tzeng, T. F., Liou, S. S., Chang, Y. S., & Liu, I. M. (2011). Kaempferol regulates the lipid-profile in high-fat diet-fed rats through an increase in hepatic PPAR α levels. *Planta medica*, 77(17), 1876-1882.
45. Gomez-Zorita, S., Lasa, A., Abendano, N., Fernandez-Quintela, A., Mosqueda-Solis, A., Garcia-Sobreviela, M. P., & Arbones-Mainar, J. M. Por Tillo, MP (2017). Phenolic compounds apigenin, hesperidin and kaempferol reduce in vitro lipid accumulation in human adipocytes. *J. Transl. Med*, 15, 237-017.
46. Ochiai, A., Othman, M. B., & Sakamoto, K. (2021). Kaempferol ameliorates symptoms of metabolic syndrome by improving blood lipid profile and glucose tolerance. *Bioscience, biotechnology, and biochemistry*, 85(10), 2169-2176.
47. Wang, M., Sun, J., Jiang, Z., Xie, W., & Zhang, X. (2015). Hepatoprotective effect of kaempferol against alcoholic liver injury in mice. *The American journal of Chinese medicine*, 43(02), 241-254.
48. Gao, J., Zhang, M., Niu, R., Gu, X., Hao, E., Hou, X., ... & Bai, G. (2021). The combination of cinnamaldehyde and kaempferol ameliorates glucose and lipid metabolism disorders by enhancing lipid metabolism via AMPK activation. *Journal of Functional Foods*, 83, 104556.
49. Lu, Y., Shao, M., Xiang, H., Zheng, P., Wu, T., & Ji, G. (2020). Integrative transcriptomics and metabolomics explore the mechanism of kaempferol on improving nonalcoholic steatohepatitis. *Food & function*, 11(11), 10058-10069.
50. Herzig, S., & Shaw, R. J. (2018). AMPK: guardian of metabolism and mitochondrial homeostasis. *Nature reviews Molecular cell biology*, 19(2), 121-135.
51. Tian, L. I., Cao, W., Yue, R., Yuan, Y., Guo, X., Qin, D., ... & Wang, X. (2019). Pretreatment with Tiliain improves mitochondrial energy metabolism and oxidative stress in rats with myocardial ischemia/reperfusion injury via AMPK/SIRT1/PGC-1 α signaling pathway. *Journal of Pharmacological Sciences*, 139(4), 352-360.
52. Garcia, D., Hellberg, K., Chaix, A., Wallace, M., Herzig, S., Badur, M. G., ... & Shaw, R. J. (2019). Genetic liver-specific AMPK activation protects against diet-induced obesity and NAFLD. *Cell reports*, 26(1), 192-208.
53. Chen, M., Zhong, J., Wang, Z., Xu, H., Chen, H., Sun, X. and Zheng, L. (2021). Fibroblast growth factor 21 protects against atrial remodeling via reducing oxidative stress. *Frontiers in Cardiovascular Medicine*, 8, 720581.
54. Hu, Y., Sun, Q., Liu, J., Jia, Y., Cai, D., Idriss, A. A., ... & Zhao, R. (2017). In ovo injection of betaine alleviates corticosterone-induced fatty liver in chickens through epigenetic modifications. *Scientific reports*, 7(1), 40251.
55. Tiihonen, K.; Saarinen, M. T; Alhoniemi, E.; Mitsuya, N. and Yamaki, G. (2016). Effect of Dietary Betaine on Metabolic Syndrome Risk Factors in Asian Males with Mild Fatty Liver. *J. of Diabetes & Metab.*, 7:7.
56. Wang, Z., Yao, T., & Song, Z. (2010). Involvement and mechanism of DGAT2 upregulation in the pathogenesis of alcoholic fatty liver disease. *Journal of lipid research*, 51(11), 3158-3165.
57. Kawakami, S.; Han, K.H. and Nakamura, Y. (2012). Effects of dietary supplementation with betaine on a nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH) mouse model. *J. Nut. Sci. Vitaminol.*, 58:371-375.
58. Jung, Y.S.; Kim, S.J.; Ahn, C.W.; Kim, Y.S.; Choi, D.W and Kim, Y.C. (2013). Alleviation of alcoholic liver injury by betaine involves an enhancement of antioxidant defense via regulation of sulfur amino acid metabolism *Food Chem. Toxicol.*, 62: 292- 298.
59. Kharbanda, K.K. (2013). Methionine metabolic pathway in alcoholic liver injury. *Curr. Opin. Clin. Nutr. Metab. Care.*, 16:89-95.
60. Kharbanda, K.K.; Todero, S.L and Ward, B.W. (2009). Betaine administration corrects ethanol-induced defective VLDL secretion. *Mol. Cell Biochem.*, 327:75-78.
61. Imbard, A., Toumazi, A., Magréault, S., Garcia-Segarra, N., Schlemmer, D., Kaguélidou, F., ... & Schiff, M. (2022). Efficacy and pharmacokinetics of betaine in CBS and cblC deficiencies: a cross-over randomized controlled trial. *Orphanet Journal of Rare Diseases*, 17(1), 1-13.
62. Yi, X.J; Kang L.; Hu, Y.; QinYing, X.; NingBo, Z. and YunLiang, J. (2009). Effect of dietary betaine supplementation on mRNA expression and promoter CPG methylation of lipoprotein lipase gene in laying hens. *J. Poult. Sci.* 46:224-228.
63. Xing, J.; Kang, L. and Jiang, Y. (2011). Effect of dietary Betaine supplementation on lipogenesis gene expression and CpG methylation of lipoprotein lipase gene in broilers. *Mol. Biol. Rep.*, 38:1975-1981.
64. Yang, W.; Huang, L.; Gao, J.; Wen, S.; Tai, Y.; Chen, M.; Huang, Z.; Liu, R.; Tang, C. and Li, J. (2017). Betaine attenuates chronic alcohol-induced fatty liver by broadly regulating hepatic lipid metabolism. *Mol. Med. Rep.*, 16(4):5225-5234.
65. Yang, W., Gao, J., Tai, Y., Chen, M., Huang, L., Wen, S., ... & Tang, C. (2016). Betaine attenuates alcohol-induced pancreatic steatosis. *Pancreas*, 45(6), 836-845.
66. Yan, X., Chen, J., Zhang, C., Zhou, S., Zhang, Z., Chen, J., ... & Tan, Y. (2015). FGF 21 deletion exacerbates diabetic cardiomyopathy by aggravating cardiac lipid accumulation. *Journal of cellular and molecular medicine*, 19(7), 1557-1568.

67. Atkinson, W.; Elmslie, J.; Lever, M.; Chambers, S. and George, P. (2008). Dietary and supplementary betaine: acute effects on plasma betaine and homocysteine concentrations under standard and post methionine load conditions in healthy male subjects. *Am. J. Clin. Nutr.*, 87(3):577-585.
68. Labinjoh, C.; Newby, D. E.; Wilkinson, I. B.; Megson, I. L.; MacCallum, H.; Melville, V.; Oon, N. A. and Webb, D. J. (2001). Effect of acute methionine loading and vitamin C on endogenous fibrinolysis.
69. Bagi, Z.; Cseko, C.; Toth and Koller, A. (2003). Vascular system by Free Radical Oxidative Stress- dysregulation of arteriolar wall shear stress and blood pressure in Hyperhomocysteinemia is prevented by chronic vitamin C treatment. *Am. J. Phys. Heart Circ.*, 285:H2277-H2283.
70. Zhang, R.; Ma, J.; Zhu, H. and Ling, W. (2004). Mild Hyperhomocysteinemia induced by feeding rats diets rich in methionine or deficient in folate promotes early atherosclerotic inflammatory process. *J. Nutr.*, 134:825-30.
71. Zheng, Z., Liu, L., Zhou, K., Ding, L., Zeng, J., & Zhang, W. (2020). Anti-oxidant and anti-endothelial dysfunctional properties of nano-selenium in vitro and in vivo of hyperhomocysteinemic rats. *International Journal of Nanomedicine*, 4501-4521.
72. Bajic, Z., Sobot, T., Skrbic, R., Stojiljkovic, M. P., Ponorac, N., Matavulj, A. and Djuric, D. M. (2022). Homocysteine, Vitamins B6 and Folic Acid in Experimental Models of Myocardial Infarction and Heart Failure—How Strong Is That Link?. *Biomolecules*, 12(4), 536.
73. Ventura, P.; Panini, R.; Verlato, C.; Scarpeta, G. and Salvioli, G. (2000). Peroxidation induces and total antioxidant capacity in plasma during hyperhomocysteinemia induced by methionine oral loading. *Metabolism*, 49:225-228.
74. Huang, R. F.; Hsu, Y. S.; Lin, H. I. and Yang, F. (2001). Folate depletion and elevated plasma Homocysteine promote oxidative stress in rats livers. *J. Nutr.*, 131:33-38.
75. Kerkeni, M.; Addad, f.; Farhat, M.; Miled, A.; Trivin, F. and Maaroufi, K. (2008). Hyperhomocysteinemia and parameters of antioxidative defense in Tunisian patients with coronary heart disease. *Ann. Clin. Bio.* 45:193-198.
76. Derouiche, F., Bôle-Feysot, C., Naïmi, D., & Coëffier, M. (2014). Hyperhomocysteinemia-induced oxidative stress differentially alters proteasome composition and activities in heart and aorta. *Biochemical and Biophysical Research Communications*, 452(3), 740-745.
77. Djuric, D., Jakovljevic, V., Zivkovic, V., & Srejovic, I. (2018). Homocysteine and homocysteine-related compounds: an overview of the roles in the pathology of the cardiovascular and nervous systems. *Canadian Journal of Physiology and Pharmacology*, 96(10), 991-1003.
78. Koohpeyma, H., Goudarzi, I., Elahdadi Salmani, M., Lashkarbolouki, T., & Shabani, M. (2019). Postnatal administration of homocysteine induces cerebellar damage in rats: protective effect of folic acid. *Neurotoxicity Research*, 35, 724-738.
79. Weiss, N. (2005). Mechanisms of increased vascular oxidant stress in hyperhomocysteinemia and its impact on endothelial function. *Current drug metabolism*, 6(1), 27-36.
80. Zhang, Z., Li, D., Luo, C., Huang, C., Qiu, R., Deng, Z., & Zhang, H. (2019). Cocrystals of natural products: Improving the dissolution performance of flavonoids using betaine. *Crystal Growth & Design*, 19(7), 3851-3859.
81. Tseng, H. C., Wang, M. H., Fang, C. H., Lin, Y. W., & Soung, H. S. (2023). Involvement of Antioxidant and Prevention of Mitochondrial Dysfunction, Anti-Neuroinflammatory Effect and Anti-Apoptotic Effect: Betaine Ameliorates Haloperidol-Induced Orofacial Dyskinesia in Rats. *Brain Sciences*, 13(7), 1064.
82. Zhang, Y., Hodgson, N. W., Trivedi, M. S., Abdolmaleky, H. M., Fournier, M., Cuenod, M., Deth, R. C. (2016). Decreased brain levels of vitamin B12 in aging, autism and schizophrenia. *PLoS one*, 11(1), e0146797.
83. Kim, J. M., Stewart, R., Kim, S. W., Yang, S. J., Shin, I. S., & Yoon, J. S. (2008). Predictive value of folate, vitamin B12 and homocysteine levels in late-life depression. *The British Journal of Psychiatry*, 192(4), 268-274.
84. Balkan, J.; Oztezcan, S.; Kucuk, M.; Cevikbas, U.; Kocak-Toker, N. and Uysal, M. (2004). The effect of betaine treatment on triglyceride levels and oxidative stress in the liver of ethanol-treated guinea pigs. *Exp. Toxicol. Pathol.*, 55: 505-509.
85. Erman, F.; Balkan, J.; Cevikbas, U.; Kocak-Toker, N. and Uysal, M. (2004). Betaine or taurine administration prevents fibrosis and lipid peroxidation induced by rat liver by ethanol plus carbon tetrachloride intoxication. *Amino Acids*, 27: 199-205.
86. Wang, L., Tu, Y. C., Lian, T. W., Hung, J. T., Yen, J. H., & Wu, M. J. (2006). Distinctive antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects of flavonols. *Journal of agricultural and food chemistry*, 54(26), 9798-9804.
87. Ren, J., Meng, S., Lekka, C. E., & Kaxiras, E. (2008). Complexation of flavonoids with iron: structure and optical signatures. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 112(6), 1845-1850.
88. Ozyurek, M., Bektasoglu, B., Guclu, K., & Apak, R. (2009). Measurement of xanthine oxidase inhibition activity of phenolics and flavonoids with a modified cupric reducing antioxidant capacity (CUPRAC) method. *Analytica Chimica Acta*, 636(1), 42-50.
89. Hong, J. T., Yen, J. H., Wang, L., Lo, Y. H., Chen, Z. T., & Wu, M. J. (2009). Regulation of heme oxygenase-1 expression and MAPK pathways in response to kaempferol and rhamnocitrin in PC12 cells. *Toxicology and applied pharmacology*, 237(1), 59-68.
90. Rice-Evans, C. (2001). Flavonoid antioxidants. *Current medicinal chemistry*, 8(7), 797-807.
91. Hsu, J. Y., Lin, H. H., Chyau, C. C., Wang, Z. H., & Chen, J. H. (2021). Aqueous extract of pepino leaves ameliorates palmitic acid-induced hepatocellular lipotoxicity via inhibition of endoplasmic reticulum stress and apoptosis. *Antioxidants*, 10(6), 903.
92. Saw, C. L. L., Guo, Y., Yang, A. Y., Paredes-Gonzalez, X., Ramirez, C., Pung, D., & Kong, A. N. T. (2014). The berry constituents quercetin, kaempferol, and pterostilbene synergistically attenuate reactive oxygen species: involvement of the Nrf2-ARE signaling pathway. *Food and Chemical Toxicology*, 72, 303-311.
93. Khadke, S., Mandave, P., Kuvalekar, A., Pandit, V., Karandikar, M., & Mantri, N. (2020). Synergistic effect of omega-3 fatty acids and oral-hypoglycemic drug on lipid normalization through modulation of hepatic gene expression in high fat diet with low streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats. *Nutrients*, 12(12), 3652.
94. Matsumoto, T., Kiuchi, S., & Murase, T. (2019). Synergistic activation of thermogenic adipocytes by a combination of PPARγ activation, SMAD3 inhibition and adrenergic receptor activation ameliorates metabolic abnormalities in rodents. *Diabetologia*, 62, 1915-1927.
95. Fang, X., Song, J., Zhou, K., Zi, X., Sun, B., Bao, H., & Li, L. (2023). Molecular Mechanism Pathways of Natural Compounds for the Treatment of Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease. *Molecules*, 28(15), 5645.
96. Martínez-Reyes, I., & Chandel, N. S. (2020). Mitochondrial TCA cycle metabolites control physiology and disease. *Nature communications*, 11(1), 102.